

THE ROLE OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN IMPROVING THE LEVEL OF HUMANITARIAN TRAINING OF SPECIALISTS OF TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES.

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Abstract: The article deals with changes in social, political and economic life of our country. In this regard, the Russian language should be considered as a mandatory component of humanitarian training of specialists in a higher educational institution of technical profile. Training of specialists of high professional level should provide not only for the study of special technical sciences, but also for the development of a spiritually rich personality with creative potential and high professional culture.

Key words: humanization, personal qualities, video course, communicative-quality, foreign-language, sociocultural, motivation, auditory, visual, motor perception, authentic, listening, formation.

The humanization of higher technical education is designed to ensure the development of individuality and personal qualities, in which a specialist in his or her life and activity will take into account the needs, regulate and correlate their needs with the needs of society.

In a higher education institution of technical profile, the Russian language should be considered as a mandatory component of humanitarian training of specialists.

In today's world of actively developing international contacts and connections in politics, economics, and culture, knowledge of the Russian language becomes a real necessity. For employers of the majority of large companies, a modern specialist is a professional in his or her field, familiar with world practice and fluent in one or more foreign languages.

The topical problem of modern didactics is the need to activate the learning process in general. One of the ways to achieve this goal is to include students in various types of activities that allow them to significantly increase their cognitive activity in the process of general development. One of the forms that can to some extent solve this problem is the use of video courses in Russian language classes, which will help to teach the language not as a sign system with a set of typical phrases, but to teach communication in Russian in professionally

significant situations. It is necessary to interest foreign languages of students of technical specialties, where traditionally Russian language is not considered to be the main, main discipline.

Working with video recordings makes it possible to make the process of mastering the Russian language communicatively and cognitively, since only video recordings provide a combination of linguistic and socio-cultural links, which is inherent in situations of real foreign language communication. At the same time, it is necessary to emphasize that watching videos should not be quantitative, but qualitative in nature. To this end, a special methodology is being developed to develop a full-fledged ability to perceive linguistic and socio-cultural material.

The international community is witnessing a global informatization of all spheres of public life. Ways of improving the effectiveness of general education are being developed, and large investments are being made in the creation and introduction of new information technologies. The state of the economy, the quality of people's lives, national security and the role of the state in the international community depend on the level of information and technological development and its pace. All developed countries and many developing countries are going through intensive processes of informatization of education.

In contrast to traditional lectures, practical and seminar classes, active forms and methods of education make it possible to bring the educational process closer to reality, imitating professional activity. However, among the problems, which are theoretically and experimentally solved by the methodology of foreign languages for special purposes, the main problem is the problem of internal and external motivation of the majority of non-linguistic higher education institutions.

Introduction of various forms of communication with the use of creative and innovative technologies, development of the ability to clearly define the situations and objectives of communication with their systematic implementation, expansion of the creative and scientific potential of students within the framework of intercultural communication provide the formation and development of a competent specialist able to adapt to the modern level and style of professional and personal communication.

The use of video materials in Russian language classes develops two types of motivation: self-motivation, when the film is interesting in itself, and motivation, which is due to the fact that the student can understand the language being studied. The use of video materials arouses students' interest

and positive emotions, which contributes to the development of linguistic interest and, undoubtedly, has a significant impact on the formation of sustainable motivation to study Russian. Motivation is also enhanced by the power of impression and emotional impact of video materials on students. Therefore, the main attention should be focused on the formation of students' personal attitude to what they see. Successful achievement of this goal is only possible, firstly, by systematically showing video films, and, secondly, by methodically organized demonstration. This brings satisfaction and gives confidence in one's own strength and desire for further improvement. It is necessary to strive to ensure that students receive satisfaction from the film through understanding the language, and not only through an interesting and entertaining story.

The students of technical universities are characterized by such psychological peculiarities as a technical mindset and lack of language skills, which are so necessary for adequate perception of language realities. An important task of the Russian language teacher is to create real and imaginary situations of communication in the Russian language class using various methods and techniques (role-playing games, discussions, creative projects, etc.). It should be noted that the use of video materials in the classroom is not only the use of another source of information. The use of video contributes to the development of various aspects of students' mental activity and, above all, attention and memory. During the inspection of the video material there is an atmosphere of cognitive joint activity. Students need to make an effort to understand the content of the video. So the involuntary attention turns into an arbitrary one, and the intensity of attention influences the process of memorization, the use of different channels of information (auditory, visual, motor perception), has a positive impact on the strength of capturing the country and language material.

The suggested method of working with video material is as follows:

- 1) teaching students to perceive the information they have seen in an organized and conscious manner;
- 2) development of students' ability to observe, classify, choose, and hypothesize based on the proposed materials;
- 3) training students to analyze and summarize the information received;
- 4) perception and expression of verbal conclusions in an authentic way;
- 5) the correct presentation of the idea contained in the shown material in the studied language, taking into account the socio-cultural norms that take place in

the foreign language communication, the skill is critically related to the seen video materials.

Thus, the psychological peculiarities of the impact of video materials on students contributes to the intensification of the educational process and create favorable conditions for the formation of communicative competence of students.

The method of using videotapes includes three stages of work: interrogation, preview and post view. Special assignments are performed, which require students to concentrate on their work.

Practice has shown that watching video materials, which ends only with an exchange of impressions about what we have seen, is not methodologically correct. Most of the information in this approach is not perceived by students. Of particular importance is the set of exercises developed for this purpose. They are both universal and indicative.

Much attention is paid to the exercises of psychological preparation for the perception of information, development of the ability to analyze linguistic and socio-cultural information, as well as the improvement of reproductive and productive speech activities of students.

When analyzing students' speech production, the following factors are assessed: the time of task performance; the total number of words in the statement of vocabulary in relation to the original video material; the degree of understanding of the position of the heroes of video material; the degree of understanding of socio-cultural realities; the percentage of damage to the reproduced information

The set of exercises also depends on the genre of video material used in each case.

Equally important is the task of introducing students from non-language universities to the cultural values of the people who speak the language. For this purpose, the use of authentic materials (drawings, texts) is of great importance. Acquaintance with the life of Russian-speaking countries takes place mainly through the text and illustrations to it. Letters, advertisements, signs, questionnaires, and menus found in modern textbooks allow students to better navigate the country of study in case of a real visit. At the same time, it is important to give students a clear picture of the life and traditions of these countries. This can be achieved through the use of educational videos, which contribute to the implementation of the most important requirement of the communicative method "...to present the process of mastering the language as an understanding of living foreign-language activity...".

In the video materials, as well as in the texts, the information about the language is present in a hidden form: it does not speak about the rules of the language, it does not offer the development of phonetic phenomena and grammatical structures, etc. However, all these tasks are potentially possible, they are provided by the creators of educational films and, as with the use of texts, are introduced into the educational process before and after watching the film.

It is necessary to pay attention to the purpose of using video materials in the process of teaching Russian language (listening or speaking). In the course of listening, the focus is on the audio range of video material containing spoken language to be heard. Students focus on the visual range and evaluate the students' ability to provide motivation and focus for the spoken language based on this visual range.

In the case of speaking, the auxiliary range is the sound range, which may or may not be used, used in a fragmented manner, only in certain cases.

In the case of audio work, the visual series is also taken into account. For example, attention should be paid to the extent to which sound synthesis is provided to understand what is audible through the visible. However, the visual range is auxiliary and the sound range is the main one.

In order to maximize the assimilation of the video material used, it is necessary to create special conditions conducive to its better perception and understanding. Thus, we can highlight the following methods of working with video materials.

1. Repeatability (these can be key scenes as well as difficult to perceive places).
2. Separating the channels of perception of information:
 - viewing a film without sound;
 - Listening to a film without an image.
3. Working with a still image.

Videos offer informative information on a variety of topics. Their selection is conditioned by the accessibility for understanding at each stage of training, correspondence of life experience and age of Russian language learners. Facts and phenomena are selected that together provide not only the disclosure of the topic, but also serve as a basis for independent thematic statements of students. The educational goal with video materials is to involve them in a critical dialogue about the film. This can happen on the basis of questions to the content

of the speech, the situation described in the film, country studies or thematic issues.

The advantage of this form of learning is that it is suitable for independent work by students. In domestic higher education pedagogy, it is widely believed that traditional forms of practice should be replaced by forms of individualization of learning (i.e., independent and individual work). However, for students to work independently in full, well-equipped video libraries, language laboratories and facilities for independent work are needed.

It should be noted that at present the volume of humanitarian disciplines for students of technical specialties is not much less than the volume of special disciplines. However, if special disciplines forming professional knowledge are based on a solid foundation of natural-science and general professional disciplines, then the disciplines of the humanitarian cycle, namely the Russian language is taught during the year. Of course, this is very little.

Due to the current economic situation it becomes necessary to give the student an opportunity not only to choose the discipline of interest to him/her, but also to determine the degree of depth of acquaintance with it. Humanitarianization as a new direction of work of technical universities is not without difficulties implemented and requires genuine enthusiasts. Thus, the formation of a high humanitarian culture of future specialists is a commandment of time.

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